

Modeling User Perception for Multi-Quality Tile-Based 360° Video Streaming

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Abstract— As virtual reality (VR) and 360° video applications continue to gain traction, multi-quality tile-based 360° video streaming has emerged as a flexible and adaptive solution for delivering high-quality immersive content while optimizing bandwidth usage. However, the presence of mixed quality levels within a single 360° video frame can adversely affect users' perceived quality. In this work, we investigate the impact of spatial quality variations across tiles and within users' viewports, and provide improved perceptual quality modeling for tiled 360° videos. To realize this goal, we introduce the Subjective Tile-based Assessment for 360° Videos (STAV360) dataset, which includes six source 360° videos, each encoded using twelve tile-based configurations, subjective ratings from 27 participants, and corresponding viewing trajectories. Based on this dataset, we propose novel tile-based and viewport-aware 360° video quality assessment (360° VQA) models that incorporate tile-level quality information and user interaction data. Experimental results show that our models outperform conventional full-frame methods by more accurately predicting perceived quality. This work provides key insights for designing perceptually-driven quality metrics and lays the foundation for more efficient and adaptive tile-based 360° video streaming strategies.

Index Terms—360° videos, immersive applications, video streaming, video quality assessment (VQA), virtual reality (VR).

I. INTRODUCTION

THE growing demand for immersive virtual reality (VR) content is driven by the rapid advancement of innovative immersive technologies. As adoption increases, the VR market is projected to exceed \$200 billion by 2029 [1]. Immersive applications not only enhance interactivity and user engagement but also deliver more compelling and memorable experiences. Nowadays, VR and 360° videos are being utilized in diverse fields including entertainment, education, cultural events, and healthcare services.

In a streaming context, ensuring an adequate quality of experience (QoE) for VR users is constrained by stringent network requirements [2]. Currently, video streaming dominates the internet traffic, accounting for 74% mobile data traffic [3]. Multimedia service providers and network operators employ innovative network paradigms and

streaming algorithms to minimize the burden on core networks while meeting users' expectations. Nonetheless, streaming VR and 360° video content pose more serious challenges due to their higher data rates and lower tolerance to latency [4]. Generally, 360° videos need to be delivered within milliseconds at 8K or higher resolutions to ensure a satisfactory experience.

To alleviate the challenges associated with 360° video transmission, tile-based streaming has emerged as a promising solution that aims to minimize the delivered content size while maintaining satisfactory QoE to end users [4], [5]. In VR, users see only a portion of the spherical scene, known as their viewport or field of view (FoV). Ideally, transmitting just the viewport portion would lead to substantial bandwidth savings. However, strict viewport-dependent streaming requires precise viewing prediction and continuous intensive processing, making it impractical for most real-life applications [6]. Instead, tile-based 360° video streaming divides the 360° video, in equirectangular projection, into smaller rectangular tiles. Since only tiles relevant to the users need to be delivered at high quality, tile-based streaming achieves notable bitrate reduction while mitigating the limitations of strict viewport-dependent streaming. Tiles are encoded, usually at multiple quality levels, and transmitted independently to be stitched again at the end user's side. Generally, uniform tiling configurations such as 5x10, 6x12, and 8x8 are commonly used in the literature, offering a practical balance between spatial granularity and computational efficiency [7], [8]. While a higher number of tiles enables more flexible streaming and finer adaptation, it also increases processing complexity and can impact the overall compression performance.

In an ideal basic tiled 360° video streaming setup, unwatched tiles are not sent, and only tiles watched by the user are delivered at high quality, resulting in substantial bandwidth reduction. However, such an approach lacks flexibility and requires perfect knowledge of future users' viewports, which are not known in advance. Given this, multi-quality tile-based 360° video streaming algorithms [9], [10], assisted by viewport prediction models, offer intelligent and flexible strategies for transmitting 360° video tiles at different

quality levels based on their relevance to the user’s viewport and on the available network resources.

Despite its advantages, applying multi-quality tile-based streaming can result in spatial quality variations within video frames, which might degrade the user’s experience. Existing tile-based streaming strategies lack comprehensive visual quality modeling that accounts for the variations in delivered tile quality. Although some researchers highlighted the importance of maintaining smooth visual quality in delivered content to improve QoE [11], [12], there has been little to no experimental effort made to quantify and validate the impact on user experience.

The influence of quality fluctuations in tile-based 360° videos on user experience remains an underexplored research area that requires serious attention. Having a good understanding and accurate modeling of perceptual quality for tiled 360° videos is vital to implementing more effective streaming algorithms and for monitoring the quality of streamed content. Recent subjective and objective 360° video quality assessment (360° VQA) methods have adapted classical VQA considering the defining characteristics of omnidirectional content. However, existing studies focus on 360° videos that are encoded at a uniform full-frame basis and fail to consider the implications of spatial quality variations, which results in multi-quality tile-based 360° video streaming.

In recent years, subjective 360° VQA experiments have been performed, aiming to understand VR users’ quality perception of omnidirectional videos [13], [14], [15], [16]. This allowed the development of new objective quality metrics. While classical VQA models have substantially improved at estimating the perceptual quality of conventional 2D videos, new 360° VQA models were needed to account for the unique characteristics of 360° videos. For instance, the spherical peak signal-to-noise ratio (S-PSNR) [17] and the weighted-to-spherical PSNR (WS-PSNR) [18] metrics modify the classical PSNR calculations to target 360° videos. While other metrics incorporate viewport information for more accurate estimation [19], to this day, existing subjective and objective 360° VQA studies have primarily focused on uniformly encoded videos. However, the presence of spatial quality variation in multi-quality tile-based 360° videos introduces an additional influencing factor that has largely been overlooked, leaving a significant gap in the accurate assessment of their perceptual quality. In view of this, this work is dedicated to understanding and modeling perceptual quality for tile-based 360° videos. Our contributions can be summarized as follows:

- STAV360 dataset development: We introduce STAV360, the first publicly available subjective dataset designed specifically for evaluating multi-quality tile-based 360° videos. It includes six 360° video sequences, each encoded using twelve distinct tile-based configurations, along with subjective quality scores and head movement trajectories from 27 participants. This dataset serves as a foundational benchmark for future research in tile-aware quality assessment and 360° video streaming. The STAV360

dataset is publicly available at: <https://github.com/SLG-European-projects/STAV360>.

- Comprehensive analysis of perceptual quality: We conduct an in-depth analysis of the subjective ratings and corresponding viewing behavior to investigate how different tile quality combinations influence perceived visual quality. Our findings reveal the critical impact of spatial quality variation on the overall user experience.
- Novel tile-based and viewport-aware VQA Models: We propose a set of objective 360° VQA models that incorporate tile-level quality statistics, accounting for overall quality and spatial variation in both the horizontal and vertical dimensions. These models include both tile-based and viewport-tile-based approaches, enabling enhanced modeling of perceptual quality. Evaluation results demonstrate that our models significantly outperform traditional full-frame methods in predicting MOS scores, confirming the benefit of spatially-aware modeling in immersive content evaluation.

In Section II of this paper, we discuss related work in the literature, highlighting the motivation behind this study. Section III introduces the STAV360 dataset and analyzes the viewport information and subjective scores, deriving valuable insights for the subjective quality of tiled 360° videos. In section IV, we introduce and formulate the objective quality features used in this work. The evaluation setup, models, and results are introduced and discussed in Section V. Finally, we conclude our work in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK & MOTIVATION

While tile-based 360° video streaming improves bandwidth efficiency and perceived quality, it also poses challenges for quality assessment. Both subjective and objective 360° VQA studies are essential to quantifying users’ perceptual experience of omnidirectional video content. Subjective evaluations, relying on mean opinion scores (MOS), provide reliable insights derived from actual VR user ratings. Objective 360° VQA metrics, on the other hand, are critical for practical applications, including real-time optimization and monitoring of 360° video streaming systems [20].

In recent years, several subjective experiments have been conducted to observe VR user interaction and perception of 360° videos in various setups. In [21], for instance, the authors performed subjective experiments to investigate the impact of viewing devices and viewport resolutions on the QoE of 8K 360° video viewing. In [22], a series of subjective tests were conducted to examine the rating consistency of users watching 360° videos using a head-mounted display (HMD) device, with comparisons made between standing and seated viewing conditions. While such studies cover important aspects of 360° video quality, further investigation is needed to understand the unique perceptual factors involved in tile-based streaming applications. The authors in [23] took the initiative towards comparing full delivery and partial delivery tile-based

streaming strategies. However, their experiment assumed uniform tile encoding scenarios and employed simulated head movements to render the content on a 2D display. In contrast, practical systems exhibit more versatile tile encoding patterns, where the user’s viewport can consist of tiles at different quality levels. The resulting spatial quality variation within delivered content may significantly impact perceived visual quality, which remains a largely underexplored aspect. Moreover, in practice, VR users equipped with HMD devices can freely navigate the spherical scenes, introducing more dynamic and individualized viewing paths.

For objective 360° VQA assessment, quality metrics have been specifically designed, considering the distinct features of spherical content. For example, the WS-PSNR improves upon traditional PSNR by assigning latitude-based weighting to address the non-uniform pixel sampling in projected frames. Similarly, the S-PSNR mitigates projection-related distortions by computing pixel-wise errors after performing uniform sphere-sampling, enabling quality comparisons across different projection formats. Some models even incorporate viewing data to focus on parts watched by the user. The viewport PSNR [24] metric computes the mean squared error (MSE) based on viewport pixels only, omitting unviewed content. While viewport-based metrics offer personalized evaluations, they also depend on precise knowledge of user viewing paths and impose considerable computational overhead, making them impractical in real-time applications.

Importantly, most existing 360° VQA methods are well-suited for assessing the quality of 360° videos encoded at a uniform full-frame basis. As tile-based 360° video streaming introduces non-uniform spatial quality distributions across frames (and users’ viewports), it adds a new layer of complexity to perceptual quality assessment. A deeper understanding of this relationship is essential for designing more perceptually aligned streaming algorithms and ultimately improving QoE in immersive video experiences. Therefore,

there is a critical need for systematic subjective evaluations and the design of new objective metrics that can better correlate with human perception of tile-based 360° videos.

In view of the persisting gap regarding subjective and objective 360° VQA for tile-based content, we dedicate this work to examining the QoE of VR users while watching 360° videos at various tile encoding patterns. To achieve this, we present the STAV360 public dataset, featuring six 8K 360° videos, each encoded with twelve tile-based configurations. A subjective study was conducted with 27 users, and the dataset includes their ratings and viewing trajectories. Based on the analysis of this data, we propose a set of novel objective 360° VQA metrics that explicitly account for spatial quality variation within video frames and within users’ viewports. The proposed metrics improve quality estimation, contributing to the development of more perceptually effective tile-based 360° video streaming systems.

III. STAV360: DATASET DESCRIPTION & ANALYSIS

A. Dataset description

The STAV360 dataset [25] comprises six source 360° videos, used to construct 72 test sequences at 12 tile encoding patterns. The dataset also includes subjective ratings and head movement (HM) trajectories of 27 users, who watched the videos using a Quest 3 VR device. All participants volunteered to take part in this experiment and gave their consent after reading the experiment description and purposes. The 360° videos in the dataset were captured using an Insta360 Action Camera X4, mounted on a fixed tripod, at 8K resolution (7680 × 3840) and 30fps. The camera settings were set to encode the videos using HEVC/H.265 at the highest possible bitrate (200 Mbps). Since the captured videos are stored at high bitrates, they can reliably be used as reference sequences for assessing encoded instances at lower rates.

FeedTheDucks

FootballFreestyling

LycabettusSunset

MuseumOfTheAncientAgora

PiraeusPort

TempleOfHephaestus

Figure 1. Snapshots of 360° videos in STAV360.

Figure 2. Tile encoding patterns in the STAV360 dataset, showing the tile encoding levels (Low, Mid, High) in each pattern. Darker color indicates higher quality.

TABLE I: SI-TI information for the dataset videos.

Video Title	SI (mean)	TI (mean)
FeedTheDucks	32.91	1.69
FootballFreestyling	27.53	2.73
LycabettusSunset	20.51	3.75
MuseumOfTheAncientAgora	14.66	1.30
PiraeusPort	16.32	0.79
TempleOfHephaestus	24.78	0.62

The dataset videos are titled FeedTheDucks, FootballFreestyling, Lycabettus-Sunset, MuseumOfTheAncientAgora, PiraeusPort, and TempleOfHephaestus. Figure 1 shows snapshots of the videos. These videos were taken in various environments and have different characteristics.

To quantify the spatiotemporal diversity of test sequences, we obtain their spatial information (SI) and temporal information (TI) metrics [26]. Table I presents the mean SI-TI values for each video across all frames. The mean SI values span from 14.66 (MuseumOfTheAncientAgora) to 32.91 (FeedTheDucks), providing a wide range of spatial complexity. Meanwhile, the mean TI values are from 0.62 (TempleOfHephaestus) to 3.75 (LycabettusSunset). In this work, we avoid sequences with high temporal dynamics as they contribute to VR cybersickness, which can distress participants and disturb their perceptual ratings.

A uniform tiling grid of 10x5 tiles (10 horizontal x 5 vertical) was adopted to have a compatible setup with practical 360° video streaming applications. Thus, each of the resulting tiles is square-shaped and has a resolution of 768x768 pixels. Each tile is then encoded using three quantization parameters (QPs) to make three encoding levels: High (QP=22), Mid (QP=32), and Low (QP=42). We used the FFmpeg software for tiling and stitching encoded tiles, and the x265 encoder (through FFmpeg’s libx265) was used for tile compression. The chosen tile configuration (10x5 tiles at 768x768 pixels) and three quality levels (QP = 22, 32, 42) reflect practical tile-based streaming implementations, where tiles are pre-encoded at multiple qualities for dynamic selection [27]. Nonetheless, exploring a broader range of tiling schemes and quality levels in future work could help capture a wider variety of real-world deployment scenarios.

For each video, a set of twelve tile encoding configurations is used to create the test sequences. A visual representation of

the tile encoding patterns is displayed in Figure 2. The tiling patterns can be grouped into the following four profiles:

- Uniform patterns: Contains three uniform tile encoding patterns, which are labeled as Pattern1_Uniform_Low, Pattern2_Uniform_Mid, and Pattern3_Uniform_High. Each of these patterns was constructed using the same QP level for all its tiles (42, 32, 22, respectively).
- Center-enhanced patterns: Contains four patterns that give higher quality to central tiles. These patterns are labeled as Pattern4_Center01, Pattern5_Center02, Pattern6_Center12, and Pattern7_GradCenter012.
- Checkerboard quality patterns: Consists of three patterns (Pattern8_Checkerboard01, Pattern9_Checkerboard-02, and Pattern10_Checkerboard12) with alternating tile quality levels.
- Randomized patterns: Contains two randomized patterns that are different for each video, where tile quality levels are assigned with equal probability to QPs 42, 32, and 22. These patterns are Pattern11_random1 and Pattern12_random2.

The selected patterns reflect diverse scenarios that can be encountered in tile-based 360° video streaming, each potentially affecting the perceptual quality in different ways.

A total of 27 participants (18 male, 9 female), aged 18–47, took part in the experiment. Following ITU-T P.919 guidelines [28], each participant completed a 20-minute session involving six 360° video contents, each with the 12 tile encoding patterns shown in randomized order (72 test stimuli in total). Test stimuli were played without audio to focus on the visual quality and avoid audio influence on given ratings. The videos were viewed using a Meta Quest 3 VR headset while seated on a swivel chair. Before starting the test, participants read the experiment description and were encouraged to ask the experimenter for clarification on any part. They were also given the option to pause the experiment to rest if needed. However, since the test duration was moderate (~20 min), they all completed the test without a break. Participants filled in a questionnaire reporting their familiarity with VR and whether they experienced dizziness during the test. 7 users (out of 27) reported slight dizziness.

Participants viewed the test stimuli using a custom Unity-based VR application on the Meta Quest 3. Using the Quest

controllers, they rated each video’s visual quality on the Absolute Category Rating (ACR) scale from 1 (bad) to 5 (excellent). Unity’s XR Interaction Toolkit handled viewing and rating interactions and was used to record HM traces, including viewing directions (as quaternions and Euler angles), timestamps, and video frames. For each user and sequence, the collected data were stored in a txt file as {Timestamp, VideoTime, VideoFrame, HeadYaw, HeadPitch, HeadRoll, HeadQuatW, HeadQuatX, HeadQuatY, HeadQuatZ}. The average tracking rate was 71.6 sample/s, which is more than twice the frame rate of the test videos.

B. Dataset analysis

To develop a meaningful understanding of how tile-based 360° video characteristics relate to user experience, a thorough analysis of the STAV360 dataset is essential. This part investigates the quality and bitrate distribution of encoded tiles and analyzes the subjective ratings and viewing traces of VR users while watching the 360° video sequences.

Tile quality distribution: As a starting point, we examine the distribution of individual encoded tiles across the three predefined quality levels: High (QP=22), Mid (QP=32), and Low (QP=42). While streaming services aim to deliver high-quality content, lower-quality tiles are often necessary in bandwidth-constrained scenarios. In typical streaming systems, each tile is pre-encoded at multiple quality levels on the server, and tile quality selection is performed as a trade-off between system cost and user satisfaction. To quantify this trade-off, we evaluate each tile in terms of bitrate (as a measure for cost) and PSNR (as a measure of objective quality). Figure 3 visualizes both bitrate and PSNR for individual tiles across the three encoding levels. Bitrate values, plotted on a logarithmic scale, reveal substantial differences as the Low encoding level (QP=42) has an average tile bitrate of just 41.12 Kbps, with most tiles falling below 100 Kbps. In contrast, the Mid (QP=32) and High (QP=22) levels average 162.28 Kbps and 1.07 Mbps per tile, respectively, reaching maximum bitrates of 817.74 Kbps and 4.54 Mbps. These substantial bitrate differences can be justified by the improvements in PSNR values. The High encoding level offers a marginal improvement in visual quality, with a mean PSNR of 46.23 dB, compared to 41.91 dB and 37.18 dB for the Mid and Low levels, respectively.

Analyzing VR user behavior: We analyze the viewing behavior of VR participants while watching the 360° videos and examine the implications of user navigation patterns in tile-based videos. The STAV360 dataset contains the viewing directions of the 27 participants for each of the 72 video instances. The yaw and pitch angles, comprising a total of 1,292,293 HM data points, are used in this analysis after being scaled to the ranges $[-180^\circ, 180^\circ]$ and $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$, respectively.

Figures 4 and 5 illustrate users’ viewing behavior while watching the six different 360° videos and demonstrate the implications of viewing behavior on tile-based content. Specifically, Figure 4 presents representative viewing traces

from five users watching each video (at Pattern3_Uniform_High encoding), showing the movement of viewport centers within the $360^\circ \times 180^\circ$ scene for the whole video length (10sec). Figure 5 complements this with aggregated heatmaps and tile-viewing percentages based on all collected data, where each unique video was watched twelve times by each of the 27 users. Together, the figures reveal how users’ attention is distributed spatially across different types of scenes.

In Figures 4a and 5a (FeedTheDucks), viewers’ traces are distributed along a long stretch of the horizontal central axis. This corresponds to the region of interest (ROI), where ducks are swimming in a lake. The heatmaps and tile viewing percentages confirm that this horizontally central area consistently attracts high attention. Users’ attention spans a wide horizontal range with limited vertical exploration. The viewing traces in Figure 4b (FootballFreestyling) are more concentrated as most users fixate on the center, where a football performer is located. This results in a more focused heatmap and higher tile-viewing percentages for central tiles, as seen in Figure 5b. The confined spatial interest shows how strongly a salient object (i.e., the performer) influences viewing behavior. Similar to FeedTheDucks, users’ HM traces while watching the LycabettusSunset video, displayed in Figure 4(c), are stretched horizontally, where the sunset occurs. The ROI here includes a view of the city and setting sun, leading to a wider distribution of attention across the central horizontal band. This also reflects on the tile heatmap in Figure 5c. While viewing the MuseumOfTheAncient-Agora video, users mainly explored the left side of the scene, where more dynamic content (i.e., moving visitors in open space) is present. Meanwhile, the right side, containing static artifacts, received less attention. This asymmetry is visible in both the trace patterns and the tile viewing percentages (Figures 4d and 5d). The attention distribution for the PiraeusPort video resembles that of FootballFreestyling. Based on Figures 4e and 5e, users focused mostly on the center, as the scene’s periphery lacks engaging content. The video titled TempleOfHephaestus (Figures 4f and 5f) features a single strong ROI where people walk and interact with a cat at a historical site. Nearly all users’ traces are focused on this region (slightly to the right of the scene’s center). The viewing heatmap and tile viewing percentages show high attention in this ROI, making this one of the most tightly clustered attention patterns.

Figure 3: Tile bitrate vs. PSNR values for each encoding level.

Figure 4: Examples of collected user viewing directions and magnified regions of interest.

Across all videos, one consistent trend emerges: users tend to focus on central areas, particularly along the horizontal axis, while vertical exploration remains limited. These navigation patterns are driven by both the structure of the video scenes and the presence of engaging objects. The distribution of tile-viewing percentages follows this, as central tiles are most frequently viewed and thus most important for user experience. These insights are leveraged in the following sections, where we propose quality features and 360° VQA models that emphasize central tile fidelity based on general trends in VR user behavior. We also implement more ambitious approaches that consider individual users' viewports for more personalized and accurate estimation.

MOS analysis: The STAV360 dataset employed the ACR method for subjective quality assessment. All 27 participants watched the full set of 72 test video sequences and rated their perceptual quality from 1 (bad) to 5 (excellent). To reduce

personal bias and improve statistical reliability, corresponding z-scores were computed and rescaled to the range [0, 100]. Subsequently, the MOS score was calculated for each of the 72 video sequences by averaging the rescaled z-scores. The distribution of rescaled z-scores is illustrated in Figure 6. The rescaled z-scores span over the range [0, 100] with a mean of 55.02 and only a few instances at the extremes.

To have a more insightful discussion and relate the subjective scores to the tile encoding patterns, we analyze the MOS scores obtained for different configurations, while considering their associated bitrate levels. Figure 7 plots the average MOS scores against the corresponding average video bitrates for each pattern, showing the spread of scores from all users and all unique videos in each encoding pattern. Several important observations relevant to the storage, streaming, and quality assessment of 360° videos emerge from this analysis.

Figure 5: Distribution of viewing directions and corresponding tile viewing percentages.

Figure 6: Distribution of calculated z-scores.

Figure 7: Bitrate vs. subjective scores for tile encoding patterns, averaged over all videos and users' scores.

Based on the results in Figure 7, using Pattern6_Center12 or Pattern10_Checker-board12 can achieve substantial bitrate reductions of approximately 19% to 29% compared to Pattern3_Uniform_High, with only a slight reduction in perceived quality. Additionally, patterns with similar bitrates often produced different subjective quality levels. For example, Pattern2_Uniform_Mid and Pattern7_Grad-Center012 yielded significantly higher MOS scores than Pattern9_Checker-board02 and the two random patterns (Pattern11_random1 and Pattern12_random2), which can be attributed to greater spatial variations in tile quality in the latter group. Similarly, Pattern4_Center01 and Pattern5_

Center02 performed better than Pattern8_Checkerboard01. Overall, center-enhanced patterns (i.e., Patterns 4, 5, 6, and 7) received high ratings, highlighting the importance of prioritizing quality in the most frequently viewed regions.

IV. OBJECTIVE 360° VQA CALCULATIONS

In this section, we introduce the features used in the objective 360° VQA models proposed in this paper. We cluster these features into three main groups, defining the clusters of implemented 360° VQA models. The first group comprises full-frame 360° VQA metrics found in the literature, which do not assume knowledge of human viewing behavior in VR. In the second group, we introduce a set of new viewport-agnostic models that operate on tile-level and leverage prior knowledge about the general behavior of VR users. In the third group, we propose 360° VQA models that utilize information about users' viewport tiles into more personalized modeling.

Before providing the models' formulation, we introduce the adopted notations. Each objective model is designed to predict the MOS_p^k values for each video instance S_p^k , where p represents the test condition (i.e., tile encoding pattern) for the video in the content session k . The full frame of an encoded video has a pixel resolution of $P_H \times P_V$. The frame is divided into $M \times N$ tiles, making each tile consisting of $\frac{P_H}{M} \times \frac{P_V}{N}$ pixels. The bitrate of tile (m, n) is denoted $b_{m,n}$. The total number of frames in each video is T . For simplicity, we omit the subscripts p and k in the following formulation, as they are consistent across all instances.

A. Full-frame 360° VQA

The first group of objective models examined in this paper consists of popular 360° VQA metrics in the literature that operate on a full-frame basis. Models in this cluster give an indication of the video overall quality and do not require information about the tiling setup or users' viewing. Specifically, we utilize the PSNR, S-PSNR, and WS-SPNR metrics. We also include the video bitrate as an additional baseline method. Although, strictly speaking, video bitrate is not a quality metric, it is often used as an optimization target. We decided to include the video bitrate here to showcase that this approach is suboptimal, and the focus should be on improving QoE through accurate 360° VQA metrics.

The PSNR is the most popular quality metric due to its simplicity and straightforward calculations. The formula for PSNR is shown in equation (1), where MAX_I denotes the maximum possible pixel value (255 for 8-bit video). $y_t(i, j)$ and $y'_t(i, j)$ are pixel values at position (i, j) in frame t within the reference and distorted frames, respectively.

$$PSNR = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T 10 \log \left(\frac{MAX_I^2}{MSE_t} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$MSE_t = \sum_{i=1}^{P_H} \sum_{j=1}^{P_V} (y_t(i, j) - y'_t(i, j))^2 \quad (2)$$

The S-PSNR calculation is similar to that of PSNR, but it utilizes uniformly distributed points on a sphere before calculating the MSE values. Samsung's tools360 [29] implementation of S-PSNR uses 655,362 precomputed sphere positions that are used, with interpolation, to determine pixel values at the mapped coordinates.

The WS-PSNR is also based on squared pixel errors. For ERP-projected videos, it entails latitude-based weights as follows:

$$WS - PSNR = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T 10 \log \left(\frac{MAX_I^2}{WMSE_t} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$WMSE_t = \sum_{i=1}^{P_H} \sum_{j=1}^{P_V} w(i, j) \cdot (y_t(i, j) - y'_t(i, j))^2 \quad (4)$$

$$w(i, j) = \cos \left(\left(j + 0.5 - \frac{P_H}{2} \right) \pi / P_H \right) \quad (5)$$

B. Tile-based 360° VQA

Although the full-frame methods presented in the previous part adapt conventional VQA to omnidirectional content, they are designed for 360° videos encoded on a full-frame basis. Particularly, they do not account for the spatial quality variation and its perceptual impact introduced in tile-based 360° video streaming. In multi-quality tile-based streaming, the encoding quality is not consistent across all parts of the video as some tiles might be delivered at higher quality levels than others, depending on the tile quality assignment algorithm and the underlying channel conditions. This in turn can affect the overall user viewing experience. Moreover, full-frame models do not consider the viewing behavior of VR users. As demonstrated in Section III-B, VR users view central parts of 360° videos the most. Intuitively, and aligning with the findings in Figure 7, central tiles carry more significance and have the highest influence on subjective quality. To address these issues, we propose computing quality measurements on a tile-level basis, which we then utilize to implement more effective models for assessing the quality of tile-based 360° videos.

In this work, we employ tile-level PSNR values, by aggregating pixel errors using the same equation in (1) but on a tile-level basis. However, we keep our formulation generic to accommodate other metrics that can be used similarly. We denote the quality measure of tile (m, n) as $Q_{m,n}$. Based on the obtained $Q_{m,n}$ values, we derive four statistical values that we utilize in our tile-based 360° VQA models. The first calculated value is the global tile-based mean quality Q_{GT} ,

which provides an overall measurement based on all video tiles and it is calculated as follows:

$$Q_{GT} = \frac{1}{M \cdot N} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N Q_{m,n} \quad (6)$$

The second statistical measure is the center tile-based mean quality Q_{CT} , and it represents the average of quality values for the $M_C \times N_C$ center tiles that start at (m_0, n_0) . In most cases, the central area of a 360° video is viewed more frequently than the rest of the scene and contributes the most to subjective quality. Therefore, we quantify Q_{CT} , based on quality measurements of central tiles, to incorporate it into our models:

$$Q_{CT} = \frac{1}{M_C \cdot N_C} \sum_{m=m_0}^{m_0+M_C-1} \sum_{n=n_0}^{n_0+N_C-1} Q_{m,n} \quad (7)$$

The other two aggregate quality indicators incorporate spatial variation measures, represented by horizontal and vertical quality differences. These measures capture the local smoothness of the video quality by quantifying the quality variations between adjacent tiles in both horizontal and vertical directions. This approach provides a more accurate reflection of the user's experience, accounting for spatially varying quality distributions within tiles and aligning better with the subjective assessments of video quality. Like the mean indicator, we compute one global and one central spatial variation measurement. The global spatial variation is comprised of mean-squared horizontal and vertical differences across the video frame, and is formulated as follows:

$$\Delta_{GT} = \sqrt{\Delta_H + \Delta_V} \quad (8)$$

Where the values Δ_H and Δ_V are computed as follows:

$$\Delta_H = \frac{1}{(M-1) \cdot N} \sum_{m=1}^{M-1} \sum_{n=1}^N (Q_{m+1,n} - Q_{m,n})^2 \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta_V = \frac{1}{M \cdot (N-1)} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} (Q_{m,n+1} - Q_{m,n})^2 \quad (10)$$

Similarly, Δ_{CT} is obtained through calculating horizontal and vertical quality variations, but only in central tiles.

$$\Delta_{CT} = \sqrt{\Delta_{CH} + \Delta_{CV}} \quad (11)$$

Where the values Δ_{CH} and Δ_{CV} are then computed as follows:

$$\Delta_{CH} = \frac{1}{(M_C-1) \cdot N_C} \sum_{m=m_0}^{m_0+M_C-2} \sum_{n=n_0}^{n_0+N_C-1} (Q_{m+1,n} - Q_{m,n})^2 \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta_{CV} = \frac{1}{M_C \cdot (N_C-1)} \sum_{m=m_0}^{m_0+M_C-1} \sum_{n=n_0}^{n_0+N_C-2} (Q_{m,n+1} - Q_{m,n})^2 \quad (13)$$

The features utilized in the proposed tile-based 360° VQA models were selected to overcome the limitations of existing full-frame methods by considering the unique characteristics of multi-quality tile-based 360° videos. First, the Q_{GT} feature is utilized to provide a global representation of the video quality, ensuring robust performance. Meanwhile, the Q_{CT} measure was formulated to capture the average quality of central tiles only. By incorporating this feature, VQA models

are explicitly encouraged to focus on regions most likely to be seen, improving perceptual relevance. Since central tiles are the most viewed in 360° videos, this is expected to improve correlation with subjective quality scores. In addition to average quality measures, the proposed tile-based 360° VQA approach also utilizes global and central tile-based spatial quality variation features (Δ_{GT} and Δ_{CT}). Humans are sensitive to spatial quality inconsistencies. As depicted in Figure 7, uniform tile encoding patterns yielded substantially better scores than patterns with high quality fluctuations. A video with all its tiles encoded at medium quality level is more acceptable to users than one with high contrast by alternating low/high quality levels. Therefore, employing Δ_{GT} and Δ_{CT} as loss terms would incorporate this information globally and centrally into more perceptually aligned quality predictions. In addition to potential improvements in prediction accuracy, working with tile-level measurements would allow for faster and more scalable computation. Precalculated tile-level metrics can be utilized for computing quality predictions instead of using pixel values for each tile encoding setup.

C. Viewport-tile-based 360° VQA

While central tiles are typically the most viewed and contribute significantly to perceived quality, this can vary depending on the specific video content. Additionally, individual users follow different viewing paths, which can influence the importance of specific tiles. The proposed viewport-tile-based 360° VQA approach addresses this by considering tiles' contributions based on users' actual viewport content. Incorporating video- and user-specific tile viewing information is expected to improve the accuracy of quality predictions. First, we find users' watched pixels within each tile to be used for identifying important tiles. We use $\psi_{t,m,n}^u(i,j)$ to indicate pixel viewing. $\psi_{t,m,n}^u(i,j)$ is set to 1 when pixel (i,j) in tile (m,n) is within the viewport of user u at a time instance t , and is set to 0 otherwise.

$$\psi_{t,m,n}^u(i,j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if pixel } (i,j) \text{ is viewed} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Since we are more interested in tile-level viewing, we denote two values that capture this information. The first one is $\Psi_{m,n}^u$, which is a binary indicator that tells whether any part of tile (m,n) , at any time, was within user's u viewport.

$$\Psi_{m,n}^u = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \exists (i,j,t) \text{ s.t. } \psi_{t,m,n}^u(i,j) = 1 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

While this quantity identifies watched tiles, it does not differentiate between viewport tiles. However, this is a simple approach that is also compatible with 360° video streaming frameworks that apply predictive tile viewing classification models. A more ambitious attempt would be to assign specific weights to each viewport tile, based on their viewing percentages. We denote $a_{m,n}^u$ to give individualized tile-level weights, based on tile viewing percentages for each user. In some 360° video streaming systems, this can be replaced by predicted tile weights or viewing probabilities to be used in quality-aware transmission. Here, we calculate $a_{m,n}^u$ for each tile and user based on actual users' viewed pixels as follows:

$$a_{m,n}^u = \frac{M \cdot N}{T \cdot P_H \cdot P_V} \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^{P_H/M} \sum_{j=1}^{P_V/N} \psi_{t,m,n}^u(i,j) \quad (16)$$

Now, we incorporate the values $\Psi_{m,n}^u$ and $a_{m,n}^u$ into viewport-tile-based metrics to provide tile-viewing-aware quality prediction. The first quantity we compute is the viewport tiles bitrate. b_{VT}^u measures the total bitrate of all viewport tiles that are viewed by a user u , and is found as follows:

$$b_{VT}^u = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N b_{m,n} \cdot \Psi_{m,n}^u \quad (17)$$

We denote Q_{VT}^u as a measure of the average quality over viewport tiles viewed by a user u . Q_{VT}^u is hence calculated as follows:

$$Q_{VT}^u = \frac{1}{M \cdot N} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N Q_{m,n} \cdot \Psi_{m,n}^u \quad (18)$$

We also assign a similar quantity that finds the weighted average of viewport tile qualities. The calculation of Q_{WVT}^u employs tile weights $a_{m,n}^u$, found by equation (16).

$$Q_{WVT}^u = \frac{1}{M \cdot N} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N Q_{m,n} \cdot a_{m,n}^u \quad (19)$$

Next, we formulate a measure for the quality variation within viewport tiles. Δ_{WVT}^u incorporates weighted horizontal and vertical quality variations within tiles viewed by user u . The weighted horizontal variation Δ_{WVT-H}^u , and the weighted vertical variation Δ_{WVT-V}^u measure local tile quality changes across the user's viewport, where the weights are assigned based on the smaller viewing percentage among each two adjacent tiles. It should be noted that by taking the minimum viewing percentage among adjacent tiles, only viewport tiles contribute to this measure even though the summation is performed over the $M \times N$ tiles, with putting emphasis on variations in most viewed areas over partially watched ones. Thus, Δ_{WVT}^u can be obtained as follows:

$$\Delta_{WVT}^u = \sqrt{\Delta_{WVT-H}^u + \Delta_{WVT-V}^u} \quad (20)$$

$$\Delta_{WVT-H}^u = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^{M-1} \sum_{n=1}^N (Q_{m+1,n} - Q_{m,n})^2 \cdot \min(a_{m+1,n}^u, a_{m,n}^u)}{\sum_{m=1}^{M-1} \sum_{n=1}^N \min(a_{m+1,n}^u, a_{m,n}^u)} \quad (21)$$

$$\Delta_{WVT-V}^u = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} (Q_{m,n+1} - Q_{m,n})^2 \cdot \min(a_{m,n+1}^u, a_{m,n}^u)}{\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} \min(a_{m,n+1}^u, a_{m,n}^u)} \quad (22)$$

Compared to tile-based 360° VQA methods, viewport-tile-based 360° VQA offers more personalized modeling that reflects the individualized user experience. Based on the user's viewing information, $\Psi_{m,n}^u$ and $a_{m,n}^u$ are used to capture the tile relevance to areas watched by the user. More specifically, $\Psi_{m,n}^u$ provides a binary indication for which tiles are watched, partially or entirely, by user u . Whereas $a_{m,n}^u$ offers a more ambitious approach that quantifies tile weights by counting the number of pixels within the tile watched by the user. Integrating either of these values into quality modeling offers more personalization for potentially improving objective metrics.

TABLE II: Summary of proposed 360° VQA models.

Objective 360° VQA metric		Input features	Computational assumptions	Relevant equations
Type	Metric			
Tile-based metrics	RidgeTile	Tile-level PSNR values $Q_{m,n}$ for all $M \times N$ tiles	Use regression models to map all tile PSNR values directly to MOS	Direct regression from $Q_{m,n}$ values
	SVRTile			
	LRStat	Statistical tile-based features: Q_{GT} , Q_{CT} , Δ_{GT} , Δ_{CT}	Rely on aggregated tile statistics with relevance to general human perception	Eq. (6)-(13)
	SVRStat			
Viewport-tile-based metrics	VT-Bitrate	Bitrate of user's viewport tiles, based on $b_{m,n}$ and $\Psi_{m,n}^u$	Sums the bitrates of viewport tiles, ignoring non-viewed tiles and assuming a direct relationship between bitrate and perceived quality	Eq. (17)
	VT-PSNR	PSNR of viewport tiles, using $Q_{m,n}$ and $\Psi_{m,n}^u$	Aggregates PSNR values of tiles within the user's viewport, neglecting non-viewed tiles	Eq. (18)
	WVT-PSNR	Weighted viewport tiles' PSNR, using $Q_{m,n}$ and $a_{m,n}^u$	Weights each tile's PSNR by the fraction of its area visible in the viewport, assuming perceived quality contribution is proportional to the visible tile area	Eq. (19)
	SVR-WVTStat	Weighted viewport tile statistical measures Q_{WVT}^u and Δ_{WVT}^u	Regression models based on aggregated tile statistics, considering perceptual factors and positional relevance	Eq. (19)-(22)
	LR-WVTStat			
	RidgeWVTStat			

Accordingly, Q_{WVT}^u and Δ_{WVT}^u are formulated as weighted measures for tile-based viewport average quality and quality variation, respectively. Therefore, through personalized modeling that integrates the user's viewing information, viewport-tile-based 360° VQA methods can enhance quality assessment.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Evaluated objective models

As described in the previous section, the models are grouped based on the information they use into: full-frame 360° VQA models, tile-based 360° VQA models, and viewport tile-based 360° VQA models.

Full-frame 360° VQA models compute quality scores across the entire frame, with no regard to the tiling configuration or user viewing behavior. This category includes four straightforward metrics: Bitrate, PSNR, S-PSNR, and WS-PSNR.

Tile-based 360° VQA models leverage the tile quality values $Q_{m,n}$, computed for each tile in the $M \times N$ tiling structure. In this study, the $Q_{m,n}$ represents the tile-level PSNR, where pixel errors are aggregated within each tile. However, the general formulation in Section IV allows for alternative quality measures to be used. Based on these tile values and their derived statistics, four tile-based models are developed and evaluated.

- RidgeTile and SVRTile predict MOS scores directly from the $Q_{m,n}$ values using ridge regression and support vector regression (SVR), respectively.
- LRStat and SVRStat use the four statistical features Q_{GT} , Q_{CT} , Δ_{GT} , Δ_{CT} as inputs, and apply linear regression (LR) and SVR, respectively.

Viewport-tile-based 360° VQA models further refine the assessment by focusing only on the tiles viewed by users:

- VT-Bitrate sums the bitrate values of the tiles within the user's viewport, corresponding to b_{VT}^u in Equation (17).
- VT-PSNR computes the aggregated PSNR of viewport tiles, substituting tile PSNR values into Equation (18) to obtain $Q_{m,n}$.
- WVT-PSNR (Weighted Viewport PSNR) uses tile-level PSNR values to calculate the weighted viewport score Q_{WVT}^u , as defined in Equation (19).
- The final three models, SVR-WVTStat, LR-WVTStat, and RidgeWVTStat, use the viewport-based statistical measures Q_{WVT}^u and Δ_{WVT}^u to fit the MOS data via SVR, LR, and ridge regression, respectively.

We note that the SVR, LR, and ridge regression models described in this part were fitted using the MOS scores of 24 video instances, belonging to two unique videos, and the rest of the sequences (48 video instances, belonging to four unique videos) were used for the final evaluation. Table II summarizes the proposed models, along with input features, computational assumptions, and associated equations.

B. Correlation with subjective MOS scores

We employed five evaluation metrics to assess the performance of the objective 360° VQA models in predicting perceptual quality: Pearson's correlation coefficient (PCC), Spearman's rank-order correlation coefficient (SROCC), Kendall's rank-order correlation coefficient (KROCC), root mean squared error (RMSE), and mean absolute error (MAE). These metrics are often used in the literature to reflect the performance of objective metrics and their ability to estimate

subjective scores [30]. Table III reports these evaluation metrics for the developed objective models.

Figure 8 shows the relationship between calculated objective metrics and subjective quality scores. The scattered points correspond to the subjective scores, where each point represents the average score of one test sequence. The dashed line represents a logistic curve fitted to these scores based on the predictions from the objective metrics.

The results provided in Table III and Figure 8 demonstrate important findings in this study. First, both tile-based metrics and viewport-tile-based metrics model groups provided substantial improvement over full-frame metrics, which are agnostic to tile configuration and tile-level qualities. Between full-frame metrics, all PSNR variations (i.e., PSNR, S-PSNR, and WS-PSNR) resulted in comparable performance, surpassing the Bitrate metric.

Among the tile-based metrics group, the best-performing models were the ones that utilize derived statistical quality measurements, including center quality and quality variation indicators. While models that directly employ tile-level qualities (i.e., RidgeTile and SVRTile) resulted in decent performance, they were not able to capture the full complexity of subjective user perception. Whereas LRStat and SVRStat, leveraging mean quality and mean quality variation with explicit attention to central tiles, achieved better performance over all evaluation criteria. Specifically, SVRStat resulted in a PCC of 0.876 and SROCC of 0.870, indicating high correlation with subjective scores.

Naturally, the best performing metrics group was the viewport-tile-based metrics, as it considers the actual user viewed tiles. We first note how the VT-PSNR and WVT-PSNR models perform marginally better than the full-frame PSNR. Just by neglecting non-watched tiles in the PSNR calculation, the PCC correlation was improved by 0.077 (for VT-PSNR) and 0.116 (for WVT-PSNR), and MAE error decreased by 1.129 and 1.492, respectively. The improved results of WVT-PSNR over VT-PSNR are attributed to utilizing tile weights, given as viewing percentages, as it

allows fully viewed tiles to contribute more than partially viewed ones. It is also worth noting that using bitrate values (even VT-Bitrate) as quality measurement is evidently a suboptimal choice with low correlation to subjective scores. This should be motivation for researchers working on streaming algorithms development, not to rely on bitrate levels as an indication of perceived quality.

Between viewport-tile-based metrics, models that employed viewport-tile statistics, i.e., weighted viewport PSNR and weighted viewport quality variation, achieved the best performance. Notably, the RidgeWVTStat model achieved the highest correlation with subjective score across all metrics, with PCC of 0.880, SROCC of 0.883, and KROCC of 0.711. It also delivered the lowest error metrics with 4.520 RMSE and 3.574 MAE. Overall, these results show the importance of considering the distribution of tile qualities among delivered tiles in multi-quality tile-based 360° video streaming.

Subjective perceived quality can be significantly influenced by the positioning of high-quality and low-quality tiles. Significant contribution to the overall perceived quality comes from central tiles, with dependency on the exact user viewing directions. These findings should be considered in quality assessment of tiled 360° videos and when designing tile-based streaming algorithms. To fully understand the contribution of each feature in the quality prediction, we fetch the parameters of the best-performing linear models, as they are easy to interpret. First, we show the function of the best linear tile-based metric (LRStat) based on learned parameters for normalized input and output data:

$$MOS_{VT} = 0.0728Q_{GT} + 0.0076Q_{CT} - 0.0025\Delta_{GT} - 0.01892\Delta_{CT} + 0.5505 \quad (23)$$

Equation (23) suggests that the global mean quality Q_{GT} has the highest contribution to the user experience, with notable negative influence from central quality fluctuations Δ_{CT} . Similar effects were seen by Q_{CT} and Δ_{GT} but with less degree.

TABLE III: Evaluation of viewport-agnostic 360° VQA methods.

Objective 360° VQA metric		PCC	SROCC	KROCC	RMSE	MAE
Type	Metric					
Full-frame metrics	Bitrate	0.534	0.536	0.457	8.572	7.474
	PSNR	0.738	0.748	0.608	6.978	5.428
	S-PSNR	0.734	0.703	0.601	7.037	5.496
	WS-PSNR	0.727	0.687	0.592	7.141	5.608
Tile-based metrics	RidgeTile	0.818	0.849	0.690	5.464	4.138
	SVRTile	0.831	0.832	0.658	5.281	3.902
	LRStat	0.868	0.874	0.700	4.716	3.732
	SVRStat	0.876	0.870	0.691	4.587	3.664
Viewport-tile-based metrics	VT-Bitrate	0.581	0.599	0.443	7.739	6.190
	VT-PSNR	0.815	0.811	0.651	5.504	4.299
	WVT-PSNR	0.854	0.845	0.672	4.947	3.936
	SVR-WVTStat	0.855	0.840	0.652	4.926	4.135
	LR-WVTStat	0.862	0.871	0.690	4.821	3.931
	RidgeWVTStat	0.880	0.883	0.711	4.520	3.574

Full-frame Metrics

Tile-based Metrics

Viewport-tile-based

Figure 8: Relationship between objective video quality metrics and subjective quality measurements (MOS).

We also put down the resulting formula for the RidgeWVTStat viewport-tile-based model, which was the best and most accurate model in this study. It should be noted that, for simplifying the formula, the viewport tile quality and viewport quality variation values were averaged over all users, dropping the u symbol, found in Equations (19) and (20). Thus, the following equation is only dependent on the values Q_{WVT} and Δ_{WVT} for viewport-tile-based MOS prediction:

$$\hat{MOS}_{WVT} = 0.0871Q_{WVT} - 0.0200\Delta_{WVT} + 0.5899 \quad (24)$$

The parameters here were also obtained for normalized input and output data. The average viewport-tile-based quality

Q_{WVT} , given as viewport tile-based PSNR, has a high positive contribution to the predicted subjective scores, with a positive parameter of 0.0871. The viewport tile-based quality fluctuation Δ_{WVT} affects the estimated MOS negatively based on the parameter -0.0200. Considering this measure has proved to be very effective in improving the quality assessment over models like the WVT-PSNR, which only relies on Q_{WVT}^u values without considering local quality changes.

C. Limitations and future work

The proposed models and analysis in this work provide valuable insights into 360° VQA for multi-quality tile-based

360° video streaming. However, some limitations remain as open opportunities for future work. For instance, in this work, we considered three tile compression levels and a single tiling setup. Streaming systems can support different tiling configurations or sets of more encoding levels. Extending quality modeling and evaluation to a wider range of configurations is a promising direction for a more comprehensive quality assessment. Additionally, we encourage researchers to explore the impact of temporal quality fluctuations, which may arise from tile quality adaptation, on the overall QoE.

Future work should also test generalizability across more diverse user populations and content types. To achieve this, large-scale datasets with large numbers of test videos and participants should be constructed. This would also enable effective training and validation of neural network models, based on tile-level metrics or tile content, toward more ambitious quality assessment.

Regarding the viewport-tile-based 360° VQA models proposed in this study, additional evaluation should be performed under viewport uncertainty conditions. Our evaluation of this metrics group relied on ground-truth viewport data, which might not be available in some applications. In proactive streaming frameworks designed for maximizing quality metrics, viewport prediction errors would translate into inaccuracies in quality assessment. Future work should investigate the robustness of viewport-tile-based 360° VQA models when relying on predicted viewports and explore potential strategies to mitigate performance degradation.

Finally, the videos in our experiment were played without audio to focus solely on the visual quality. In realistic VR experiences, spatial audio can influence viewing behavior and attention, which may affect the overall QoE. Future studies should consider the implications of including audio for more realistic modeling.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work focused on investigating the perceived quality experienced by VR users when viewing multi-quality tile-based 360° videos. First, we constructed the STAV360 public dataset, comprising subjective ratings and viewing trajectories of VR users who watched 360° videos at different tile encoding configurations. Following a comprehensive analysis of collected data, we developed novel quality assessment models tailored for tile-based 360° video streaming applications. Specifically, we proposed a set of tile-based 360° VQA models that utilize tile-level quality information, as well as viewport-tile-based models that incorporate users' tile viewing distributions. By comparing the predicted quality scores with users' MOS, we demonstrated that leveraging tile-level data significantly improves assessment accuracy, especially when utilizing viewing information, compared to traditional full-frame methods. Furthermore, our results show that while the average viewport quality is important, quality variations within the viewport can negatively influence user experience. These findings highlight the importance of considering both spatial quality distribution and user interaction when designing quality metrics and developing tile-based streaming algorithms for 360° video.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Kumar, Naveen. "Virtual Reality Statistics 2025: Users & Trends." DemandSage, 28 May 2025, www.demandsage.com/virtual-reality-statistics.
- [2] Ruan, Jinjia, and Dongliang Xie. "A survey on QoE-oriented VR video streaming: Some research issues and challenges." *Electronics* 10.17 (2021): 2155.
- [3] Ericsson. *Ericsson Mobility Report: June 2025*. June 2025, <https://www.ericsson.com/en/reports-and-papers/mobility-report>.
- [4] Mahmoud, Moatasim, et al. "A survey on optimizing mobile delivery of 360 videos: Edge caching and multicasting." *IEEE access* 11 (2023): 68925-68942.
- [5] Xie, Lan, et al. "360ProbDASH: Improving QoE of 360 video streaming using tile-based HTTP adaptive streaming." *Proceedings of the 25th ACM international conference on Multimedia*. 2017.
- [6] Yaqoob, Abid, Ting Bi, and Gabriel-Miro Muntean. "A survey on adaptive 360 video streaming: Solutions, challenges and opportunities." *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* 22.4 (2020): 2801-2838.
- [7] Hosseini, Alireza M., and Jacob Chakareski. "Comparative analysis and performance evaluation of adaptive 360° video dash streaming solutions." *2024 IEEE 26th International Workshop on Multimedia Signal Processing (MMSp)*. IEEE, 2024.
- [8] Zhang, Lei, et al. "Tbsr: Tile-based 360 video streaming with super-resolution on commodity mobile devices." *IEEE INFOCOM 2024-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications*. IEEE, 2024.
- [9] Mahmoud, Moatasim, et al. "Optimized Tile Quality Selection in Multi-user 360° Video Streaming." *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society* (2024).
- [10] Park, Sohee, et al. "Adaptive streaming of 360-degree videos with reinforcement learning." *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*. 2021.
- [11] Ban, Yixuan, et al. "An optimal spatial-temporal smoothness approach for tile-based 360-degree video streaming." *2017 IEEE Visual Communications and Image Processing (VCIP)*. IEEE, 2017.
- [12] Long, Kaixuan, et al. "Optimal wireless streaming of multi-quality 360 VR video by exploiting natural, relative smoothness-enabled, and transcoding-enabled multicast opportunities." *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia* 23 (2020): 3670-3683.
- [13] Gutierrez, Jesus, et al. "Subjective Evaluation of Visual Quality and Simulator Sickness of Short 360° Videos: ITU-T Rec. P. 919." *IEEE transactions on multimedia* 24 (2021): 3087-3100.
- [14] Li, Chen, et al. "Bridge the gap between VQA and human behavior on omnidirectional video: A large-scale dataset and a

- deep learning model." Proceedings of the 26th ACM international conference on Multimedia. 2018.
- [15] Anwar, Muhammad Shahid, et al. "Measuring quality of experience for 360-degree videos in virtual reality." *Science China Information Sciences* 63 (2020): 1-15.
- [16] Fremerey, Stephan, et al. "Subjective test dataset and meta-data-based models for 360° streaming video quality." 2020 IEEE 22nd International Workshop on Multimedia Signal Processing (MMSP). IEEE, 2020.
- [17] M. Yu, H. Lakshman, and B. Girod, "A framework to evaluate omnidirectional video coding schemes," in Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Mixed Augmented Reality, 2015, pp. 31–36.
- [18] Y. Sun, A. Lu, and L. Yu, "Weighted-to-spherically-uniform quality evaluation for omnidirectional video," *IEEE Signal Process. Lett.*, vol. 24, no. 9, pp. 1408–1412, Sep. 2017.
- [19] Xu, Mai, et al. "Viewport-based CNN: A multi-task approach for assessing 360 video quality." *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 44.4 (2020): 2198-2215.
- [20] Li, Yixuan, et al. "Perceptual quality assessment of face video compression: A benchmark and an effective method." *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia* (2024).
- [21] Arai, Daichi, et al. "Influence of Display Devices and Field of View on Subjective Quality of Experience Evaluation of 8K 360° Videos." 2024 International Symposium on Multimedia (ISM). IEEE, 2024.
- [22] Elwardy, Majed, et al. "On the Consistency of 360 Video Quality Assessment in Repeated Subjective Tests: A Pilot Study." *EAI Endorsed Transactions on Industrial Networks and Intelligent Systems* 11.1 (2024): 1-22.
- [23] Schatz, Raimund, Anatoliy Zabrovskiy, and Christian Timmerer. "Tile-based streaming of 8K omnidirectional video: Subjective and objective QoE evaluation." 2019 Eleventh international conference on quality of multimedia experience (QoMEX). IEEE, 2019.
- [24] Chakareski, Jacob, et al. "Viewport-driven rate-distortion optimized 360° video streaming." 2018 IEEE International conference on communications (ICC). IEEE, 2018.
- [25] Mahmoud, Moatasim, et al. "STAV360: A Dataset for Subjective Tile-based Assessment of 360° Videos." 2025 12th International Conference on Information Technology (ICIT). IEEE, 2025.
- [26] International Telecommunication Union. Recommendation ITU-T P.910: Subjective Video Quality Assessment Methods for Multimedia Applications. International Telecommunication Union, 2008. <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-P.910>.
- [27] Zhang, Xiaoyi, et al. "Cooperative tile-based 360 panoramic streaming in heterogeneous networks using scalable video coding." *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology* 30.1 (2018): 217-231.
- [28] Recommendation, I. T. U. T. "Subjective test methodologies for 360° video on head-mounted displays." International Telecommunication Union (2020): 919.
- [29] Samsung Electronics. (2016). 360 Tool. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Samsung/360tools>.
- [30] Valiandi, Ioanna, et al. "Subjective and Objective VQA of Video Codecs for UHD Video Streaming." 2024 9th International Conference on Frontiers of Signal Processing (ICFSP). IEEE, 2024.